

The Effect Of Corporate Social Responsibility (Csr) Programs At The Palm Oil Mill Companies On Regional Development In South Labuhan Batu District

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Abdul Rajab Pasaribu, ⁽²⁾Badaruddin, ⁽³⁾Syaad Affifuddin,
⁽⁴⁾Rudjiman ⁽⁵⁾Syafrizal Helmi
Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine and analyze the CSR implementation whether it has been operating effectively and influenced by the district government or otherwise. In addition, it is also to examine whether there is any effect of the application of CSR to the regional development or otherwise. This study is conducted in the district of South Labuhan Batu in North Sumatera province, while the location is at the palm oil mill companies, government offices in the district and surrounding communities who are associated with the environment of those palm oil mill companies. The explanatory design is used by applying the method of survey in the South Labuhan Batu district and the variables consist of role of government, CSR implementation and regional development.

The population is divided into three categories: (i) the existing palm oil mill companies in the South Labuhan Batu district of 21 companies; (ii) south Labuhan Batu district government, represented by the Head of sub-districts and villages; (iii) the society of South Labuhan Batu district as the stakeholders of 275,067 people. While the sampling method is chosen as many as 100 respondents. The study concludes that the role of government partially has a positive and significant impact on the CSR implementation, and CSR variable partially has a positive and significant effect on the regional development. The role of government partially has a positive and significant impact on regional development, and the role of government is the more dominant variable when compared with CSR variable.

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, regional development, sustainable development.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This study deals with the theme of a large implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) to the regional development in South Labuhan Batu District which is based on the Act No. 26 of 2007 of spatial planning. According to Rustiadi et al. (2006), the region can be defined as a geographical unit with certain specific boundaries where the components of the region interact with each other functionally. So that the restriction area is not always physical and certain but often is dynamic.

The regional development goal is to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of resources scattered in the region, in order to realize development in the region. The regional development policy in principle to support and strengthen regional development (Ary, 1999). According to Adisasmita (2008), the dimensions of the region is a factor that must be taken into account in analyzing and determining a program or project which is put into development planning. Moreover, the regional development precisely being implemented in a growing economy by relying on the public management resources (common and public resources), among others, forestry, fisheries, or regional management (Sugiharto, 2006). This regional development has a complexity of problems related to the management of these resources, intensify environmental development or associated with implementing a moral issue. At least there are three components that will need to be addressed: natural resources, human resources and technology that commonly referred to as the three pillars of regional development (Zen, 1999).

The CSR is an idea that makes the company no longer faced with the responsibility that rests on a single bottom line, i.e. the value of the company (corporate value) which is reflected in its financial condition only but the responsibility of the company should be based on the triple bottom lines that are also concerned about the social and environment (Daniri, 2008). The definition of CSR may vary, one of the similarities is that CSR can not be separated from the interests of shareholders and stakeholders of the company. Thus through CSR, a company must be able to integrate economic, social and environmental considerations into their business strategies and activities without having to be stuck on issues of law (Melis et al. 2009).

Elkington (1997) mentions the 3P formulation of 'people, planet and profits', means a business not only has a purpose for profit, but also the welfare of people, and ensure the sustainability of the environment. Since then CSR is seen as a new paradigm in business and used as management tools by companies. Moreover, CSR becomes a standard or a new principle in business management that emphasizes the ethical considerations, social and environmental as embodied in the Global Compact and the Global Reporting Initiative. A survey conducted by Perrini et al. (2006) on 395 companies in Italy found that companies that apply CSR can improve the image of the company (90%), increasing the opportunities for cooperation with local communities (76%) and motivate employees to be more ethical (56%). These have been agreed by Quazi and O'Brien (2000); Maignan (2001); Singhapakdi et al. (2001); Maignan and Ferrell (2003) mentioned that

the companies that implement CSR will increase the sense of ethics, morality and personal values of the managers and employees involved. A survey conducted by AccountAbility in 2007 revealed the responsible measurement index ranging from 0-100, where Sweden has the highest rank (81.5), followed by Denmark (81.0), Finland (78.8) and Malaysia (63.7). Meanwhile, the Korean government uses CSR activities to restructure its business recovery in order to get out of the financial crisis in 1998. They realized that the purpose of CSR is not only concerned with economic benefits alone but also taking into account ethical, environmental, and social morality (Choi & Aguilera, 2009).

Unfortunately there are still have the CSR practices in the form of philanthropy capitalism with the characteristics of (1) the CSR management is the foundation that formed the company, so that the velocity of money remains in the company (2) the beneficiary does not participate in determining the choice of programs (3) the agenda of CSR program is determined by the company (4) government regulation of CSR based on the corporate agenda (Ardianto & Machfidz, 2011). Under these conditions the behavior of employers still vary. Kotler and Nancy (2005) classifies the concept of CSR into two forms/approaches namely, (i) the traditional approach where the company is only implementing CSR as merely of obligations or fulfill the mandate of the law; (ii) new approach that companies implementing CSR as a business strategy. According Tanudjaja (2009), the differences on the meaning of CSR by companies will lead to differences in the implementation of CSR among companies as well, depending on how the companies interpret CSR.

According Indarti (2010), there are many differences in the understanding of the concept of CSR in Indonesia, where many institutions and industries that provide different understanding and scope to look at the concept of CSR. These differences makes the implementation of CSR has a slow progress including the absence of a comprehensive legal instrument regulating the CSR. Legal instrument is needed to encourage the implementation of CSR, in fact, as stated in the Government regulation No. 47 of 2012 that the limited liability company has the social and environmental responsibility held by directors as the subject to the Law.

According Anatan (2008), the implementation of CSR should be in the corridors of corporate strategy to achieve the basic of the company's business goal. CSR development requires a systematic and complex stages. First, the efforts to look at and assess the needs of the

community by identifying the problems that occur and seek appropriate solutions. Second, action plans have been made along with budgets, schedules, evaluation indicators, and resources necessary for the company. Third, monitoring activities through direct visits or through surveys. Fourth, conduct regular evaluation and reporting to be used as a guide to strategy and development of the next program. To support and ensure the attainment of the CSR objectives and achieve an effective balance between environment and development, it required a good governance involving the government as one of the actors in the system settings (Rees, 2006).

Currently, the activities of CSR programs in an attempt to improve the welfare of society is divided into three categories, namely: (1) the activities of CSR programs that are charity, which boosted by religious motivations; (2) the CSR program that helps small businesses partially. Today more companies are realizing the importance of CSR-oriented approach to increase productivity and encourage self-reliance, one of the activities is to help small businesses; (3) activities of CSR-oriented programmes are building the competitiveness of society such as education programs, health, and infrastructure designed synergistically with the strengthening of the economy so as to increase the index of human development at the local level (Situmorang, 2010).

This research was conducted on companies of palm oil mills in South Labuhan Batu district in North Sumatra Province. The main objective of this study was to examine the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility at the company of palm oil mills in South Labuhan Batu district. Specifically, the purpose of this study is to:

1. Examine and analyze whether the application of CSR has been operating effectively.
2. Examine and analyze whether there is influence of the district government in encouraging the implementation of CSR in South Labuhan Batu district?
3. Examine and analyze whether there is an influence of CSR implementation on the regional development.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Stakeholders Theory

The stakeholders theory defined by Freeman and Reed (Ulum, 2009) is a group of people or individuals who identified may affect the activities of the company or can be affected by the activities of the company. De Wit and Mayer (Duran & Radojicic, 2004) argues that the shareholders, employees, suppliers, bank, customers, governments and communities play an

important role in the organization (acting as stakeholders). Thus, the corporations must take into account all the interests and values of the stakeholders.

The linkage between individuals, organizations and society can be viewed as a 'social contract', based on the definition of the political economy theory, stakeholders, and legitimacy (Ramanathan, 1976; Williams, 1999; Deegan, 2002). The organizations play an important role in the community and have a responsibility to be recognized in the community. Implementation of corporate social responsibility is one of the mechanisms that can be used to communicate with stakeholders and as the entrance for the organization to make a profit (Badjuri, 2011). Freeman (1984) defines stakeholder as a group or individual who can affect the achievement of certain goals. While Biset (1998) briefly defines stakeholder as a person with an interest or concern on the issue.

Definition of stakeholders have changed substantially over the past four decades. At first, the shareholder is seen as the only stakeholder of the company. This view is based on the arguments presented by Friedman stated that the company's main goal is to maximize the prosperity of its owner. However, Freeman expand the definition of stakeholder to include more constituents, including groups that are considered unfavorable (adversarial group) as specific interest groups and regulators (Roberts 1992). Gray et al (1994) mention that the company's survival depends on stakeholder support and the support should be sought. Stakeholders basically able to control or have the ability to influence the use of economic resources employed by the company. The power possess by the stakeholders has a restriction on the use of limited economic resources (capital and labor), access to influential the media, the ability to manage the company or the ability to influence the consumption of goods and services produced by the company (Deegan, 2000).

Meanwhile, Jalal (2011) identified at least 75 definitions of stakeholders. However, the entire definition contains two principles: (i) principle of corporate legitimacy, that the company should be managed to provide benefits to stakeholders; (ii) principle of stakeholders' fiduciary, that the companies should create wealth which not limited to the interests of shareholders but also for the interests of stakeholders, namely all those with an association against the company such as suppliers, customers, governments, local communities, investors, employees, political groups, and trade associations. In fact, stakeholder theory is able to broaden the perspective of the company management and introduces the relationship between the power of

companies and stakeholders, however, this theory has a limitation. Gray et al. (1997) suggest that the weakness lies in the focus of stakeholder theory only on the ways that companies use to manage it's stakeholders. The company is directed to identify stakeholders that are considered important and influential and the company's attention will be directed to the stakeholders that are considered beneficial for the company.

2.2 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

A corporation established by the shareholders for profit (Lee, 2005) or an obligation to the company to implement CSR is considered contrary to the company's main goal which is for profit. Although initially the company was created to serve the interests of religion and state (Bertens, 2000). Milton Friedman believes that the companies often shirking their responsibilities. He opposes the CSR movement known with his words: "The only social responsibility of the company is increasing the profit." He is sarcastically even mention CSR which does not bring any benefits directly to the company as an action of robbing the shareholders' money.

2.2.1 Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility in Indonesia

A study by Mukti Fajar (2010) concerning the application of the provisions of CSR in multinational companies, private and state-owned companies in Indonesia shows the shape of CSR implementation is been running well but the government should develop regulations that can be used as a reference for the companies in implementing an effective CSR, precise and measurable, providing incentives in the form of tax deductions. On the other hand the company must report its CSR activities to the community on a regular basis in the form of social reporting.

According Indarti (2010), several companies successfully implemented CSR as a corporate strategy that made through the activities of the company to stakeholders such as responsibility towards our employees, shareholders, suppliers, involve and engage the SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) in production activities, creating employment opportunities, and give back to the community benefits. Griffin and Ebert (1998) added that corporate social responsibility is the responsibility of social environment relating to the way a business is acting against the group and other personals in social environment.

2.2.2 Factors Affecting the Implementation of CSR

Some of the factors that affect the implementation of company's CSR used in this study include: 1) litigation

factor, 2) society demands factor, 3) consumer demand factor, 4) company awareness factor, 5) funds availability factor.

2.2.3 Role of Government on Developing CSR

In developing the CSR culture, it takes the role of government in the form of regulation. Indonesia as a strategic geographical tropical forest that serves as the lungs of the world. The government regulation No. 47 of 2012 on Social and Environmental Responsibility confirms the annual report of company must includes financial performance, social and environment. In Europe, the obligation to carry out the CSR is realized through the creation of the annual financial statements.

2.2.4 The Local Government Policies

The local government has the authority to manage its territory based on regional autonomy laws. Autonomous regions (OTDA) which is universally known as decentralization, not just a political administrative process involving the delegation of authority to local governments alone but more important is the transfer of decision-making process to plan, implement and accelerate development activities by their own regions and the results are intended to people prosperity in the region. The implementation of decentralization is a response to the failure of the centralized system of national development and the desire to obtain the benefits of the various regions and a sense of fairness in the allocation of natural resource management outcomes.

2.2.5 The Model Implementation of the Local Government Role

There are several models of the role of local government in mediating the relationship between CSR program with the regional development by establishing as follows:

1. Institute of CSR

A well-recognized institution is can be known by the local community because of it's contribution i.e. adoption of human resources in the community as the members so it reduces the unemployment. In an effort to bridge the fund management of company's CSR program, it is important for local governments to participate directly in implemmentatio of CSR funds.

The institute is expected to be a mediator in implementing CSR programs in order to accelerate the regional development.

2. CSR Forum

This forum was established for the purpose of communication and interaction between the government, employers and society as corporate or, on the other hand this forum is expected could also synergizing that the government development planning programs do not overlap with the CSR planning program by the corporate. The forum was established based on consultation between the government and the corporate community.

2.3 Regional Development Concept

The approach applied in the regional development in Indonesia is very diverse because it influenced by the development of theories and models of regional development and socio-economic order, the system of government as well as the administration enhancement. The potential growth of regional development will help boost sustainable economic growth through a more rational distribution of the population, increasing employment and productivity (Mercado, 2002).

According to the Directorate of Strategic Area Development (2002), there are basic principles in the regional development as follows:

1. As a growth center. The regional development is not only concern on an internal affair of the region but be aware of the distribution or influence growth that can be generated for the surrounding regions, even nationally (Alkadri et al., 1999).
2. The regional development requires an effort of development collaboration between regions and as a key requirement for the successful of regional development.
3. The pattern of regional development is an integration of the areas covered in the region through equity approach.
4. In the regional development, the market mechanism should also be a requirement for regional development planning.

2.4 Previous Researches

Table 1. The Summary of Previous Researches

No	Author	Title	Method	Findings
1	Sri Indarti (2010)	The influence of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and organizational culture on job satisfaction and business performance in Riau Province	Path Analysis	Strong organizational culture has strong relationship with CSR so as to improve business performance of enterprises
2	Rimba Kusumadilaga (2010)	The influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on the value of the company to profitability as a moderating variable	Regression Analysis	CSR disclosure has a significant effect on the value of company.
3	Suciyati (2010)	Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility in relation to Good Corporate Governance (A Study in PT. APAC Inti Corpora)	Descriptive Analysis	The concept of CSR was originally only a moral obligation, has now turned into a liability as a responsibility in law.
4	Yuliana (2008)	Influence on the company characteristics on CSR disclosure and its impact on investor reaction	Partial Least Square	The characteristics of company that affect the level of disclosure is the profile and concentration of ownership
5	Angling Mahatma Pian KS (2010)	Effect of the characteristics of enterprises and government regulation on CSR disclosure based on the annual reports in Indonesia	Multiple Regression	Factors that affect CSR disclosure is proxied through ownership of government stock, foreign ownership, government regulation, type of industry, company size and profitability.
6	Mackmud and Djakman (2008)	The effect of ownership structure on CSR disclosure in the annual report of the company: An empirical study on public listed companies of Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2006.	Multiple Regression	Foreign ownership does not has a significant effect on the CSR disclosure and institutional ownership is unable to assert the significant influence to the CSR disclosure.
7	Amran and Devi (2008)	The Impact of Government and Foreign Affiliate Influence on Corporate Social Responsibility (The Case of Malaysia)	Multiple Regression	The government affect the development of CSR in Malaysia, while affiliation with foreign parties showed no significant influence on the development of CSR in Malaysia
8	Rosmasita (2007)	Factors that influence the social disclosure in the annual financial statements of manufacturing companies in the JSE	Multiple Regression	There is significant influence between the companies' factors on CSR disclosure .
9	Anggraini (2006)	A disclosure of social information and factors affecting social disclosure in the annual financial statements	Multiple Regression	Almost all the companies reveal the economic performance as been stated in IAS (PSAK) 57.
10	Sembiring (2005)	Characteristics of enterprise and social responsibility disclosure. an empirical study on the listed companies in the JSE	Multiple Regression	Size, profile and size of the board have a significant effect on the company's CSR

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

2.5 Hypothesis

Based on the conceptual framework of the view above, the proposed research hypotheses as follows:

1. Implementation of CSR in South Labuhan Batu district has not run effectively.
2. The district government has a role in encouraging the implementation of CSR in the South Labuhan Batu district.
3. There is the effect of the application of CSR to the regional development.

3.0 DISCUSSION

3.1 Validity and Reliability of Instruments

3.1.1 Validity Test

To measure the validity of the questionnaire provided to the respondents, the product moment correlation formula is used. While, reliability is the degree of precision or accuracy shown by the research instrument. The value of R_{table} with the initial of 40 respondents and 5% alpha is 0.312.

It found the results of validity test results of CSR, role of government and the regional development variables have Corrected Item-Total Correlation more than the value of 0.312, then all the items are declared valid.

3.1.2 Realibility Test

Table 2. Realibility Test

Variable	Cronbach alpha	Instrument of Cranbach alpha	Remarks
CSR	0.876	0.8	Reliable
Role of Government	0.826	0.8	Reliable
Regional Development	0.939	0.8	Reliable

3.2 Societal Perceptions

3.2.1 Descriptive of Societal Respondents

The descriptive analysis in this study is based on gender, age, religion, education level, years of service, and respondent's job title and department/unit. It found that most of society age is 41-50 years as much as 36.75%, while at least they were age of 20-30 years as much as 17.95%. Then, as much of 79.49% are male and the remaining of 20.51% are women, and in terms of religion, as many of 111 respondents (94.87%) are Muslim and the remaining as many of 6 respondents (5.13%) are Protestant Christians. Lastly, majority of respondents with a high school education level as many of 38 respondents (32.48%).

3.2.2 Classical Assumption Tests

1. Normality Test

Table 3. Normality Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		117
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	9.48962021
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.107
	Positive	.049
	Negative	-.107
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.156
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.138

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

This test is performed using Kolmogorov-Smirnov approach. If the value Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed) above the significant value of 5%, means that the residual variables are distributed normally (Situmorang and Lufti, 2014). As depicted in Table 5.21, it shows that the value Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) was 0.138 which is above the significant value of 0.05. In other words, the residual variables are normally distributed, means that there is no difference between the theoretical distribution with empirical distribution or the data is considered normal.

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

This is used to test the regression model whether there is inequality or difference in the residual variance from other observations. As shown in below Figure of the scatter plot graph, the dots are randomly spread or does not form a specific pattern, as well as the spread above or below zero on the axis Y. This means the heteroscedasticity is not occur in regression models.

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity Test

3. Multicollinearity Test

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
1 CSR	.222	4.509
Role of Government	.222	4.509

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

As depicted in the above Table, it shows the VIF values < 5, and tolerance values > 0.1, this means there is no multicollinearity in the data.

3.2.3 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

This method is used to determine the effect the relationship of the independent variables and the dependent variable.

1. Determinant Test

The coefficient of determination measures how far the ability of the model to explain variations in the independent variables or it's predictor.

Table 5. Determination Test Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.815 ^a	.664	.658	9.57250

a. Predictors: (Constant), Peran_Pemerintah, CSR

b. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The value of R = 0.815 means that the relationship of CSR and the role of government on the regional development is 81.5% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.658 means that CSR and the role of government explain the variations of regional development by 65.8% and the remaining of 34.2% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

2. Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

This test shows whether all the independent variables included in the model have jointly influence on the dependent variable.

Table 6. Uji f (Anova) ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20604.343	2	10302.172	112.429	.000 ^b
	Residual	10446.135	114	91.633		
	Total	31050.479	116			

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

b. Predictors: (Constant), The Role of Government, CSR

The F value is 112.429 with a significance level of 0.000, while the F_{table} at alpha 5% is 2.68. Therefore F > F_{table} and the level of significance 0.000 < 0.05 indicates that the independent variables CSR and the role of government simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on regional development.

3. Partial Significant Test (t Test)

Table 7. Partial T Test Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	8.197	3.355		2.443	.016
1 CSR	.273	.137	.230	1.992	.049
Role of Government	1.299	.248	.605	5.242	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The CSR variable affects positively and significantly to the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.049) below 0.05. and $t (1.992) > t_{table}$ indicates if the CSR variable increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase by 0.237 units. Meanwhile, the variable of role of government has a positive and significant influence on the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.00) below 0.05. and $t (5.242) > t_{table}$ indicates if the variable role of government increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase by 1.299 units.

The calculation results of multiple regression analysis using SPSS are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Regional Development} &= 8.20 + 0.27 \text{ CSR} + 1.30 \text{ Role of Government} \\ \text{Sig} &= (0.16) \quad (0.049) \quad (0.000) \end{aligned}$$

3.2.4 Classical Assumption Tests

1. Normality Test

Table 8. Normality Test One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		46
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	4.22565989
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.102
	Positive	.102
	Negative	-.072
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.690
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.728

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

As depicted in Table 5.30, it shows that the value Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) was 0.728 which is above the significant value of 0.05. In other words, the residual variables are normally distributed, means that there is no difference between the theoretical distribution with empirical distribution or the data is considered normal.

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

As shown in below Figure of the scatter plot graph, the dots are randomly spread or does not form a specific pattern, as well as the spread above or below zero on the axis Y. This means the heteroscedasticity is not occur in regression models.

Figure 3 Heteroscedasticity Test

3. Multicollinearity Test

Table 9. Multicollinearity Test Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
1 CSR	.776	1.288
Government	.776	1.288

a. Dependent Variable: Region

As depicted in the above Table, it shows the VIF values < 5, and tolerance values > 0.1, this means there is no multicollinearity in the data.

3.2.5 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

1. Determinant Test

Table 10. Determinant Test Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.818 ^a	.669	.654	4.32281

a. Predictors: (Constant), Government, CSR

b. Dependent Variable: Region

The value of R = 0.818 means that the relationship of CSR and the role of government on the regional development is 81.8% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.654 means that CSR and the role of government explain the variations of regional development by 65.4% and the remaining of 34.6% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

2. Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

Table 11. Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1625.080	2	812.540	43.482	.000 ^b
	Residual	803.529	43	18.687		
	Total	2428.609	45			

a. Dependent Variable: Region

b. Predictors: (Constant), Government, CSR

The F value is 43.482 with a significance level of 0.000, while the F_{table} at alpha 5% is 2.68. Therefore $F > F_{table}$ and the level of significance $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the independent variables of CSR and the role of government simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on regional development.

3. Partial Significant Test (t Test)

Table 12. Partial Significant Test (t Test)
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	10.108	4.474		2.259	.029
1	CSR	.451	.102	.438	4.402	.000
	Government	.853	.165	.514	5.161	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Region

The CSR variable affects positively and significantly to the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.00) below 0.05. and $t (4.402) > t_{table}$ indicates if the CSR variable increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase by 0.451 units. Meanwhile, the variable of role of government has a positive and significant influence on the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.00) below 0.05. and $t (5.161) > t_{table}$ indicates if the variable role of government increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase by 0.853 units.

The calculation results of multiple regression analysis using SPSS are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Regional Development} &= 10.11 + 0.45 \text{ CSR} + 0.85 \text{ Role of Government} \\ \text{Sig} &= (0.29) \quad (0.000) \quad (0.000) \end{aligned}$$

3.3 A Combination of Data of Community and Government

3.3.1 Classical Assumption Tests

1. Normality Test

Table 13. Normality Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		163
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	8.39556997
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.101
	Positive	.053
	Negative	-.101
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.287
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.073

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

As depicted in Table 5.35, it shows that the value Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) was 0.728 which is above the significant value of 0.05, means that there is no difference between the theoretical distribution with empirical distribution or the data is considered normal.

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

As shown in below Figure of the scatter plot graph, the dots are randomly spread or does not form a specific pattern, as well as the spread above or below zero on the axis Y. This means the heteroscedasticity is not occur in regression models.

Figure 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

3. Multicollinearity Test

Table 14. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
1 CSR	.292	3.430
Role of Government	.292	3.430

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

As depicted in the above Table, it shows the VIF values < 5, and tolerance values > 0.1, this means there is no multicollinearity in the data.

3.3.2 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

1. Determinant Test

Table 15. Determinant Test
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.818 ^a	.668	.664	8.44788

a. Predictors: (Constant), Role of Government, CSR

b. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The value of R = 0.818 means that the relationship of CSR and the role of government on regional development is 81.8% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.664 means that CSR and the role of

government explain the variations of regional development by 66.4% and the remaining of 33.6% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

2. Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

Table 16. Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	23025.837	2	11512.918	161.321	.000 ^b
Residual	11418.666	160	71.367		
Total	34444.503	162			

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development
b. Predictors: (Constant), Role of Government, CSR

The F value is 161.321 with a significance level of 0.000, while the F_{table} at alpha 5% is 2.68. Therefore $F > F_{table}$ and the level of significance $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the independent variables of CSR and the role of government simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on regional development.

3. Partial Significant Test (t Test)

Table 17. Partial Significant Test (t Test)
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	7.781	2.717		2.863	.005
CSR	.356	.099	.303	3.595	.000
Role of government	1.152	.178	.546	6.477	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The role of government variable affects positively and significantly to the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.00) below 0.05. and $t (6.477) > t_{table}$ indicates if the role of government variable increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase by 1.152 units.

The calculation results of multiple regression analysis using SPSS are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Regional Development} &= 10.11 + 0.45 \text{ CSR} + 0.85 \text{ Role of Government} \\ \text{Sig} &= (0.29) \quad (0.000) \quad (0.000) \end{aligned}$$

3.4 The Effect of Role of Government on CSR

3.4.1 Determinant Test

Table 18. Determinant Test
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.842 ^a	.708	.707	6.71742

a. Predictors: (Constant), Role of Government

The value of $R = 0.842$ means that the relationship of CSR and the role of government on regional development is 84.2% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.708 means that the role of government affects the CSR by 70.8% and the remaining of 29.2% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

3.4.2 Partial Significant Test (t Test)

The t statistic is used to test whether the hypothesis will be accepted or rejected. If $t < t_{table}$, then H_0 is accepted or rejected H_a , whereas if $t > t_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a accepted. If the significance level below 0.05, then H_0 is rejected and H_a accepted.

Table 19. Partial Significant Test (t Test) Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	6.719	2.095		3.207	.002
Role of Government	1.510	.076	.842	19.780	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CSR

The role of government variable affects positively and significantly to CSR implementation as seen from the significant value (0.00) below 0.05. and $t (19.780) > t_{table}$ indicates if the role of government variable increase by one unit, the CSR implementation (Y) will increase by 1.15 units.

Figure 5. Regression Model

Based on the results of the above regression test, then a summary table of regression comparison is drafted to see the comparison. Based on the table above, it shows that there is no difference between the perception of the public, companies and governments. Each regression model showed that the role of government has a significant and positive influence on CSR implementation, and the role of government has a positive and significant impact on regional development as well as the implementation of CSR affects positively and significantly to the regional development.

Table 20. A Summary of Comparison of Regression Results

Comparison of Regression Results	Community	Government	Combination
R	0.815	0.818	0.818
Goodness of fit	0.658	0.654	0.664
The effect of role of government and CSR on regional development	112.429	43.482	161.321
The effect of CSR on regional development	1.992	4.402	3.595
The effect of role of government on regional development	5.242	5.161	6.477
The effect of role of government on CSR	-	-	19.78

3.5 The Effect of role of government (partnership, economy, informational) towards the implementation of CSR

To view the role of government that consists of partnership, economy, informational towards implementation of CSR, the study conducts further testing which is path analysis test.

Table 21. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.849 ^a	.721	.716	6.61096

a. Predictors: (Constant), partnership, economy, informational

The value of $R = 0.849$ means that the relationship of role of government and CSR implementation is 84.9% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.716 means that the implementation of CSR affect the regional development by 71.6% and the remaining of 28.4% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

Table 22. ANOVA
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17970.124	3	5990.041	137.057	.000 ^b
	Residual	6949.066	159	43.705		
	Total	24919.190	162			

a. Dependent Variable: CSR

b. Predictors: (Constant), partnership, economy, informational

Based on the ANOVA test, the F value is 137.057 with a significance level of 0.000, while the F_{table} at alpha 5% is 2.68. Therefore $F > F_{table}$ and the level of significance $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the independent variables of role of government consists of partnership, economy, informational simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on CSR implementation.

Table 23. Coefficients
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.366	2.163		3.867	.000
	Informational	.711	.330	.184	2.158	.032
	Economy	1.158	.660	.138	1.755	.081
	Partnership	2.663	.474	.564	5.620	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CSR

The informational variable affects positively and significantly to the CSR implementation as seen from the significant value (0.032) below 0.05. and $t (2.158) > t_{table}$ indicates if the informational variable increase by one unit, the CSR implementation (Y) will increase by 0.184 units. Meanwhile, the economy variable has a positive and insignificant influence to the CSR implementation as seen from the significant value (0.08) below 0.05. and $t (1.755) > t_{table}$ indicates if the economy variable increase by one unit, the CSR implementation (Y) will not increase. The economy variable has a positive and insignificant influence to the CSR implementation as seen from the significant value (0.00) below 0.05. and $t (5.620) > t_{table}$ indicates if the economy variable increase by one unit, the CSR implementation (Y) will increase by 0.564 units.

Table 24. Summary of Results of Path Coefficient Structure Sub Line 1

From	To	Standard Coefficient B	T	F	R ²	E
Informational	CSR	.184	2.158	137.057	0.716	0.284
Economy		.138	1.755			
Partnership		.564	5.620			

3.6 The influence of planning, CSR implementation and mentoring on regional development

Achda (2006) states with a consistent and sustainable of CSR implementing means it foster a sense of acceptance of the existence of the company. To view each of CSR implementation consists of planning, implementation and mentoring to the regional development, thus to do further testing using a path analysis.

Table 25. Model Summary

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.781 ^a	.611	.603	9.18526

a. Predictors: (Constant), mentoring, planning, implementation
 b. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The value of R = 0.781 means that the relationship of CSR implementation and regional development is 78.1% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.603 means that the CSR implmentation affect the regional development by 60.3% and the remaining of 29.7% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

Table 26. ANOVA
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21029.824	3	7009.941	83.087	.000 ^b
	Residual	13414.679	159	84.369		
	Total	34444.503	162			

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development
 b. Predictors: (Constant), mentoring, planning, implementation

Based on the ANOVA test, the F value is 83.087 with a significance level of 0.000, while the F_{table} at alpha 5% is 2.68. Therefore F > F_{table} and the level of significance 0.000 < 0.05 indicates that the independent variable of CSR implementation consists of planning, implmentation and mentoring simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on regional development.

Table 27. Coefficients
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	13.451	2.956		4.550	.000	
1	Planning	.298	.543	.085	.548	.584
	Implementation	.368	.565	.133	.651	.516
	Mentoring	2.548	.542	.582	4.697	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The planning variable has a positive and insignificant effect to the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.584) below 0.05. and $t(0.5481) > t_{table}$ indicates if the planning variable increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will not increase.

Table 28. The Summary of Results of Path Coefficient

From	To	Standard Coefficient β	T	F	R ²	E
Planning	Regional Development	.085	.548	83.087	0.603	0.397
Implementation		.133	.651			
Mentoring		.582	4.697			

3.7 The role of government influence on Regional Development

To view the role of government that consists of partnership, economy, informational towards the regional development, the study conducts further testing which is path analysis test.

Table 29. Model Summary
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.804 ^a	.647	.640	8.74410

a. Predictors: (Constant), Partnership, Economy, Informational

The value of R = 0.804 means that the relationship of role of government and regional development is 80.4% indicates very close relationship. While the Adjusted R Square of 0.640 means that the role of government affect the regional development by 64% and the remaining of 36% can be explained by other factors not examined in this study.

Table 30. ANOVA
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22287.480	3	7429.160	97.165	.000 ^b
	Residual	12157.023	159	76.459		
	Total	34444.503	162			

a. Dependent Variable: Regional development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Partnership, Economy, Informational

Based on the ANOVA test, the F value is 97.165 with a significance level of 0.000, while the F_{table} at alpha 5% is 2.68. Therefore $F > F_{table}$ and the level of significance $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the independent variable of role of government consists of partnership, economy, informational simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on regional development.

Table 31. Coefficients
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	10.412	2.861		3.639	.000
1 Informational	1.164	.436	.256	2.671	.008
Economy	2.683	.873	.271	3.073	.002
Partnership	1.812	.627	.327	2.891	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Regional Development

The informational variable affects positively and significantly to the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.008) below 0.05. and $t(2.671) > t_{table}$ indicates if the role of government variable (informational) increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase. Meanwhile, the economy variable has a positive and significant influence on the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.002) below 0.05. and $t(3.073) > t_{table}$ indicates if the role of government (economy) variable increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase. Finally, the partnership variable has a positive and significant influence on the regional development as seen from the significant value (0.004) below 0.05. and $t(2.891) > t_{table}$ indicates if the role of government (partnership) variable increase by one unit, the regional development (Y) will increase.

Table 32. Summary of Results of Path Coefficient

From	To	Standart Coefficient B	T	F	R ²	E
Informational	Regional Development	.256	2.671	97.165	.640	0.36
Economy		.271	3.073			
Partnership		.327	2.891			

3.8 Discussion

3.8.1 CSR Implementation in Palm Oil Mill Companies

The CSR implementation is a firm commitment to contribute to sustainable economic development with attention to corporate social responsibility and focuses on the balance between social, economic and environment (Untung, 2008). In South Labuhan Batu district, the perspective of CSR implementation in palm oil mill companies is still diverse. It is not a creative program that aims to achieve the goal of sustainable development based on the pillars of economic, social and environment but most of them only meet government regulations, appropriate philanthropic vision of founder or shareholders. As a result, CSR programs that run often not well planned, unsustainable and lack of coordination with local government.

Based on the interviews with several companies, shareholders and management of the company strongly supports the implementation of CSR. This is due to the company's awareness that CSR becomes inevitable demands. To achieve the goal of the company is not only influenced by internal factors but also the surrounding community. Thus, the company believes that the CSR program can establish a harmonious relationship with the community.

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Conclusion

1. Simultaneously the CSR variable and the role of government simultaneously has a positive and significant impact on regional development.
2. The role of government partially has a positive and significant impact on the CSR implementation. The CSR variable partially has a positive and significant effect on regional development. While, the role of government partially has a positive and significant effect on regional development whereby the role of government will be more dominant variable when compared with CSR variable.
3. Based on the goodness of fit test of R Square value of 0.707, means that the regional development can be explained by the role of the government and CSR by 70.7% and the remaining 29.3% explained by other factors not examined in this study.
4. Based on the path analysis test on variables of role of government towards CSR implementation, only informational and partnership variables have a positive and significant impact, while the economy variable has an insignificant effect on the CSR implementation.
5. Based on the path analysis test on variables of CSR implementation towards regional development, only mentoring variable has a positive and significant impact, while implementation and planning variables have an insignificant effect on regional development.

4.2 Recommendation

1. The economy variable has a insignificant effect on the CSR implementation. For the government needs to consider the economic impact on the company that organizes CSR through media publications etc.
2. In the CSR implementation, implementation and planning variables have insignificant effect on regional development. For that companies need to consider aspects such as planning to attract stakeholders or people involved in planning activities such as the local NGOs and have credibility in the delivering the CSR programs, in collaboration with local governments in terms of development programs. Thus the programs work better and have considerable benefits.
3. The South Labuhan Batu district government needs to be more proactive in raising the potential of the existing CSR, ranging from socialization program partnership, formed a special division that handles CSR activities etc. that would made the CSR implementation better.

Reference

- Achda, B. Tamam. (2006). Konteks sosiologis perkembangan CSR dan implementasinya di Indonesia, Makalah Seminar Nasional. A promise of Gold Rating: Sustainable CSR, Jakarta.
- AccountAbility. (2007). The State of Responsible Competitiveness 2007. AccountAbility, London.
- Ardianto, Elvinaro & Machfudz, M Dindin. (2011). Efek kedermawanan Pebisnis dan CSR, Elex Media, Jakarta
- Badjuri, A. (2011). Faktor-Faktor Fundamental, Mekanisme Corporate Governance, Pengungkapan Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Perusahaan Manufaktur dan Sumber Daya Alam di Indonesia, Jurnal Dinamika Keuangan dan Perbankan, 3(1), 38 - 54
- Chariri, A. (2011). Teori Legitimasi dan Pengungkapan Sosial-Lingkungan, <http://staff.undip.ac.id/akuntansi/anis/2011/04/21/teori-legitimasi-pengungkapan-sosial-lingkungan/>
- Clay, J. (2005). Exploring the links between International Business and Poverty Reduction: A Case Study of Unilever in Indonesia (An Oxfam GB, Novib, Oxfam and Unilever Indonesia joint research project, Oxfam GB, Novib Oxfam, Netherland, and Unilever, 2005)
- Diana, Z., & I Putu Pande, H. S. (2003). Analisis Pengaruh Luas Pengungkapan Sosial dalam Laporan Tahunan Perusahaan terhadap Reaksi Investor (Studi Kasus pada Perusahaan High-Profile di Bursa Efek Jakarta). Simposium Nasional Akuntansi VI.
- Dahli, L. & Siregar, V. S. (2008). Pengaruh Corporate Social Responsibility terhadap Kinerja Perusahaan (Studi Empiris pada Perusahaan yang Tercatat di Bursa Efek Indonesia pada Tahun 2005 dan 2006). Simposium Nasional Akuntansi XI. Pontianak.
- Devina, F., Suryanto, L., & Zulaikha. (2004). Pengaruh Karakteristik Perusahaan Terhadap Pengungkapan Sosial dalam Laporan Tahunan Perusahaan Go Public di Bursa Efek Jakarta (BEJ). *Jurnal Maksi*, 4, 161-177.
- Eddy, R. S. (2005). Karakteristik Perusahaan dan Pengungkapan Tanggungjawab Sosial : Study Empiris pada Perusahaan yang Terdaftar di Bursa Efek Jakarta. Simposium Nasional Akuntansi VII.
- Fajar, M. (2010). Tanggung Jawab Sosial Perusahaan di Indonesia, Studi tentang Penerapan dan ketentuan CSR pada Perusahaan Multinasional, Swasta Nasioanl dan BUMN di Indonesia, Pustaka Pelajar Yogyakarta

- Fahrizki, A. (2010). Faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhi CSR, Tesis Universitas Diponegoro. Unpublished.
- Gunawan, A. (2008). Membuat Program CSR Berbasis Pemberdayaan Partisipatif.
- Hahn, T., Figge, F., & Barkemeyer, R. (2007). Sustainable Value Creation among Companies in the Manufacturing Sector. *International Journal of Environmental Technology and Management*, 7, 496-512.
- Hadi, N. (2011). Corporate Social responsibility, Ghara Ilmu, Yogyakarta
- Herawati, V. (2008). Peran Praktek Corporate Governance sebagai oderating Variabel dari Pengaruh Earning Management terhadap Nilai Perusahaan. Simposium Nasional Akuntansi XI. Pontianak.
- Jalal. (2011). Konsep dan Teori Pemangku Kepentingan, bahan pelatihan Manajemen Pemangku Kepentingan. Bogor, 18-19 mei 2011 <<http://www.csrintonesia.com/data/articles/>>
- Jalal. (2012). CSR Kelas Dunia untuk BUMN Kelas Dunia, Bisnis & CSR Nomor 27 Edisi 9-15 Juli 2012
- Keputusan Menteri BUMN No.:Kep-236/MBU/2003 tentang Program Kemitraan BUMN dengan Usaha Kecil dan Program Bina Lingkungan.
- Keputusan Menteri Keuangan Nomor 316/KMK.016/1994 tentang Pedoman Pembinaan Usaha Kecil dan Koperasi melalui Pemanfaatan Dana dari Bagian Laba Badan Usaha Milik Negara.
- Keputusan Menteri Keuangan Nomor 1232/KMK.013/1989 tentang Pedoman Pembinaan Pengusaha Ekonomi Lemah dan Koperasi melalui Badan Usaha Milik Negara.
- Keputusan Menteri Negara Pendayagunaan BUMN/Kepala Badan Pembina BUMN Nomor Kep-216/M-PBUMN/1999 tentang Program Kemitraan dan Bina Lingkungan BUMN.
- Kasali, R. (2003). Manajemen Publik Relations, Grafiti, Jakarta
- Kotler, P., & Nancy, L. (2005). Corporate Social Responsibility: Doing the Most Good for Your Company and Your Cause, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- Komala, L. (2009). Ilmu Komunikasi: Perspektif, Proses dan Konteks, Widya Padjajaran, Bandung
- Kuntari, Y., & Sulistyani, A. (2007). Pengaruh Karakteristik Perusahaan Terhadap Pengungkapan Tanggungjawab Sosial dalam Laporan Tahunan Perusahaan Indeks Letter Quality (LQ 45) Tahun 2005. *ASET*, 9(2), 494-515.
- Kurniawan, R. (2008). Analisis Good Corporate Governance, Kualitas Laba, dan Nilai Perusahaan pada Perusahaan Manufaktur yang Terdaftar di BEJ. Thesis, Akuntansi UNDIP.
- Leimona, B., & Aunul, F. (2008). CSR Pelestarian Lingkungan: Mengelola Dampak :Positif dan Negatif, Jakarta: Indonesia Business Links
- Maidatul, M., Eko, N., & Naning, A. W. (2008). Perancangan Model Pengukuran Kinerja CSR Pada Pengembangan Bisnis Ukm Dari Pt.Ytl Jawa Timur, Jurusan Teknik Industri, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (ITS) Surabaya.
- Majalah Bisnis dan CSR. (2007). Regulasi Setengah Hati, Edisi Oktober 2007.
- Marlia. (2008). Pentingnya Implementasi Corporate Social Responsibility pada Masyarakat Indonesia. [terhubung berkala] 28 Maret 2009. <http://mamrh.wordpress.com/2008/07/21/53/>
- Morimoto., Ash., & Hope. (2004). Corporate Social Responsibility Audit : from Theory to Practice, Cambridge: the Judge Institute of Management, University of Cambridge.
- Nurlela & Islahudin. (2008). Pengaruh Corporate Social Responsibility terhadap Nilai Perusahaan dengan Prosentase Kepemilikan Manajemen sebagai Variabel Moderating. Simposium Nasional Akuntansi XI.
- Nursahid, F. (2006). Tanggung Jawab Sosial BUMN, Primamedia, Depok
- Nursyahid, F. (2008). CSR bidang Kesehatan dan Pendidikan, Jakarta: Yayasan Indonesia Business Links.
- O'Donovan, G., (2002). Environmental Disclosures in The Annual Report: Extending the Applicability and Predictive Power of Legitimacy Theory, *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 15(3), 344-371.
- Peraturan Menteri Negara BUMN Nomor Per-05/MBU/2007 tentang Program Kemitraan BUMN dengan Usaha Kecil dan Program Bina Lingkungan.
- Perrini, F., Pogutz, S., & Tencati, A. (2006). Corporate social responsibility in Italy: state of the art, *Journal of Business Strategies*, 23(1), 65-91.
- Poerwanto. (2010). Corporate Social Responsibility, Pustaka Pelajar: Yogyakarta
- Rajagukguk, E. (2010). Konsep Dan Perkembangan Pemikiran Tentang Tanggung Jawab Sosial Perusahaan, <[Http://Www.Ermanhukum.Com](http://Www.Ermanhukum.Com)>
- Rakhiemah, A. N. & Agustia, D. (2009). Pengaruh Kinerja Lingkungan terhadap Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Disclosure dan Kinerja Finansial Perusahaan Manufaktur yang Terdaftar di Bursa Efek Indonesia. Simposium Nasional Akuntansi XII. Palembang.
- Retno, S.H. M., Wasidi, S., Cahyono, T. W., & Ilonav. O. S. (2010). Implementasi CSR Dalam Mendukung Pengembangan Masyarakat Melalui Peningkatan Peran Pendidikan
- Reza, R. (2009). Corporate Social Responsibility Antara Teori dan Kenyataan, Cetakan pertama, Yogyakarta: MedPres.

- Rice, Robert C. (1983). The Origin of Basic Economic Ideas and their Impact on New Order Policies, *Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies*, 19, 2.
- Rifai, B. (2012). Mengoptimalkan Peran Pemerintah Lokal dalam Tanggung Jawab Sosial Perusahaan Daerah, *Majalah Bisnis dan CSR* Edisi 22-28 Oktober 2012
- Seungho, C., & Ruth V. Aguilier. (2011). A CSR dynamics in South Korea and Japan: A comparative analysis
- Suharto, E. (2007). Corporate Social Responsibility: What is and Benefit for Corporate. <http://www.policy.hu/suharto>. Accessed on 19 Oct 2009.
- Suharto, E. (2010). CSR & Comdev Investasi Kreatif Perusahaan Di Era Globalisasi. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Suthisak K., & Frederic, W. S. (2006). Interpretation of CSR in Thai Companies. *Journal of Corporate citizenship*, <http://britannia.com/bps/additional/content/18/22097290/Interpretations-of-CSR-in-Thai-Companies>.
- Suranta, E. & Merdistuti, P. P. (2004). Income Smoothing, Tobin's Q, Agency Problem dan Kinerja Perusahaan. Simposium Nasional Akuntansi VII. Denpasar Bali, 2-3 Desember.
- Suratmo, Sribugo (2008), "implementasi CSR di Perusahaan" makalah yang disajikan pada Sminar Dua Hari, Corporate Social Responsibility: Strategy, management and Leadership, Intipesan.
- Supomo, S. (2004). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) dalam Prinsip GCG in Republika, 20 Oktober
- Sutopoyudo. (2009). Pengaruh Penerapan Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) terhadap Profitabilitas Perusahaan. Sutopoyudo's Weblog at <http://www.wordpress.com>. Accessed on 30 Oct 2009.
- Undang-undang Nomor 40 Tahun 2007 tentang Perseroan Terbatas.
- Undang-undang Nomor 19 Tahun 2003 tentang Badan Usaha Milik Negara.
- Undang-undang Nomor 20 Tahun 2008 tentang Usaha Mikro, Kecil dan Menengah.
- Untung, Hendri Budi, 2008, Corporate Sosial Responsibility, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta
- Urip, S. (2014). Strategi CSR Tanggung Jawab Sosial Perusahaan. Tangerang: Literati.
- Wahyujatmiko, B. S. (2012). Tantangan CSR Sawit di areal Transmigrasi, *Majalah Bisnis dan CSR*, Nomor 31 Edisi 22-28 Oktober 2012
- Widjaja, G., & Yeremia, A. P. (2008). Resiko Hukum & Bisnis Perusahaan Tanpa CSR, Cetakan pertama, Jakarta: Forum Sahabat.
- Yuniati G. (2000). Analisis Pengungkapan Informasi Laporan Tahunan pada Perusahaan yang Terdaftar di Bursa Efek Jakarta. Simposium Nasional Akuntansi III.
- Zeghal, D., & Ahmed, S. A. (1991). Comparison of Social Responsibility Information Disclosure Media Used by Canadian Firms. *Accounting Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 3(1), 38-53.